

Title: Deriving insights from an occupational incident reporting system to enhance understanding of musculoskeletal injury among nurses and midwives

Abstract

Aim: To improve understanding of factors that contribute to nursing workforce musculoskeletal injuries. Primary goals included describing nurse, midwife and injury characteristics related to musculoskeletal workplace compensation claims in Victoria, Australia, and developing a risk-identification framework for workplace incidents that occurred during staff-assisted patient/resident movement and were reported in the Victorian Health Incident Management System (VHIMS).

Design and methods: Observational data were collected prospectively between July 2017 and December 2021 via the Victorian government compensation scheme (WorkSafe Victoria) and the incident reporting systems (VHIMS) from two Victorian health services, that also provided residential aged care. Over three iterations, a 7-item risk-identification coding framework was developed and tested with VHIMS workplace incidents that occurred during staff-assisted patient/resident movement, and resulted in a health workforce musculoskeletal injury, or a patient/resident fall.

Results: Of 1,936 nursing workforce *compensation scheme claims* (average claimant age 43 years (SD13), 90% female (n=1,741/1,936) and 4% midwives (n=74/1,936)), the mean incapacity was 152 days (SD199), resulting in 150 FTE of lost work, at a cost of \$14,325,109, per year. The *risk-identification coding framework* was successfully applied to VHIMS incidents that occurred during staff-assisted patient/resident movement. The staff *musculoskeletal injuries* most frequently involved the trunk (60%, n=449/748), and risk factors included patient/resident participation or behaviour (72%, n=540/748) and load (65%; n=484/748); and *patient/resident falls* most frequently occurred during transfers (39%, n=748/1,935) or walking (30%, n=584/1,935), and risk factors included patient/resident participation or behaviour (94%, n=1,820/1,935) and load (55%, n=1,062/1,935). Staff-assisted patient/resident movement contributed to 41% of all-cause staff musculoskeletal injuries, and 28% of all-cause patient/resident falls.

Conclusion: Nursing and midwife musculoskeletal injuries carry significant individual and workforce costs. Risk factors were easily identified with the new novel data coding framework, which could be used to support clinical teams in developing data-driven solutions to prevent staff injuries and patient/resident falls.

Keywords: Injury; falls; compensation; risk-factors; assisted-movement; incident, manual handling, risk.

Reporting Method: Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE); extension for cross-sectional studies.

Patient or Public Contribution: No Patient or Public Contribution.

Trial and Protocol Registration: As this study used an observational design, trial registration was not required.

Introduction

The nursing and midwifery workforce experience high levels of musculoskeletal injuries in the workplace¹⁻⁹, and while some injuries may result in a compensation claim, up to 90% of the injuries are either not reported or managed within the workplace¹⁰⁻¹². These musculoskeletal injuries come at a high cost to the individual and contribute to the global nursing and midwifery workforce shortage¹³.

It has been previously reported that manual handling is in everything nurses do, and as such, nursing and midwifery musculoskeletal injuries can occur during a range of tasks¹⁴. A common high-risk task is staff-assisted movement for patients in healthcare, and residents in aged care (long-term care), as it accounts for up to one-in-three nursing musculoskeletal injuries¹⁵. Over the last two decades, lifting equipment has been routinely introduced into patient and resident care in developed countries, with the aim of reducing nursing musculoskeletal injuries, and while there is evidence that lifting equipment has reduced these injuries, the certainty of the evidence is low due to the non-randomised nature, or nil effect, of several studies^{3-8,16}. Data are urgently needed to better understand factors that contribute to nursing and midwifery workforce musculoskeletal injuries that occur during staff-assisted patient/resident movement, and to develop novel data-driven solutions to help mitigate the risks of this high-risk activity.

In Victoria, Australia, there are around 90,000 registered nurses and midwives¹⁷ and over an extended period (2006-2015) this workforce in Victorian have experienced an annual rate of 15 compensation claims per 1000 persons, indicating that nursing and midwifery is a high-risk profession^{9,18}. The objective of this study was to gain a more in-depth understanding of factors that contribute to nursing and midwifery workforce musculoskeletal injuries, with a focus on injuries that occurred during staff-assisted patient/resident movement in health and aged care. The primary aims were to (i) describe the staff and injury characteristics for nursing and midwife musculoskeletal injuries that resulted in a WorkSafe Victoria compensation claim in Victoria (Australia); and to (ii) develop and test a risk-identification coding framework to extract data from free text responses within health service and aged care occupational incident reporting systems (known as the Victorian Health Incident Management System (VHIMS)), specific to incidents that occur during staff-assisted patient/resident movement. The secondary aims were to (i) determine the ratio between lost work for musculoskeletal compensation claimants, compared to hours worked by the Victorian nursing and midwifery workforce; (ii) apply the coding framework to VHIMS incidents to report the risk factors associated with staff musculoskeletal injuries and patient/resident falls, as well as (iii) report the proportion of all-cause staff musculoskeletal injuries and patient/resident falls, that occurred during staff-assisted patient/resident movement based on VHIMS data.

Methods

Ethics approval

This study received Ethics Approval from the Human Research Ethics Committees at Cabrini Health Human (reference number 08-21-08-17); Eastern Health (reference number LR22-022-86171) and Monash University (reference number 31866). This observational study is reported according to the STROBE checklist (Appendix 1). For the WorkSafe Victoria and the health service data, a waiver of consent was approved by the Human Research Ethics Committees due to the nature of collecting de-identified, aggregate, routinely collected data.

Study design

This study used a prospective observational design to report claimant and injury characteristics for nursing and midwife musculoskeletal compensation claims and develop and test a risk-identification

coding framework to extract data from free text responses within the VHIMS health service (including aged care) occupational incident reporting systems. Key study activities are presented in Figure 1. It is noted that in Australia, nurses and midwives are part of the Healthcare and Social Assistance workforce, and this is the largest industry in Australia, accounting for 15% of the national labour force ¹⁹.

Figure 1: Key study activities

Study settings

WorkSafe Victoria: WorkSafe Victoria (also known as the Victorian WorkCover Authority) is an organisation that manages the state’s workers’ compensation scheme and funds health services and wage replacement benefits for people with accepted claims ²⁰. With a few exceptions, WorkSafe Victoria provides insurance to the Victorian workforce, and over the last decade there have been between 26,200 and 29,500 claims per year ²⁰. Accepted compensation claims for wage replacement have a demonstrated causal relationship between work and the injury or illness, and must extend beyond 10 days of work absence, as these first 10 days are the employers responsibility.

Victorian Health Services: In 2022, the public and private participating health services had a combined 2,100 inpatient beds, and these included emergency departments, acute services, rehabilitation services, as well as residential aged care services (noting the private health service

ceased their residential aged care service part-way through this study's data collection period). In Victoria, health services use the Victorian Health Incident Management System (VHIMS) to report and review patient/resident and staff incidents, and it has been reported that staff believe that organisation-wide incident management can improve safety²¹. In addition, in Australian hospitals, the Australian Commission on Safety and Quality in Health Care require "leaders of a health service organisation establish and maintain systems and processes to support clinicians to deliver comprehensive care, and establish and maintain systems to prevent and manage specific risks of harm to patients during the delivery of health care" and that each "health service organisation has organisation-wide incident management and investigation systems"²².

Data collection

WorkSafe Victoria: Prospective WorkSafe Victoria data collection extended from July 2017 until December 2021 (4.5 years). Inclusion criteria included adult (18+ years) nursing and midwifery professionals in Victoria who experienced a musculoskeletal injury that resulted in an accepted workers' compensation claim. The nursing and midwifery professionals could be employed in any setting, including health care, aged care and the community. Accepted occupation codes included: 2321 Nurse Managers; 2322 Nurse Educators and Researchers; 2323 Registered Nurses; 2324 Registered Midwives; 2325 Registered Mental Health Nurses; and 2326 Registered Developmental Disability Nurses²³. Exclusion criteria included non-musculoskeletal injuries such as burns, needle stick injuries and mental health conditions.

Characteristics and outcomes: Claimant characteristics included age, gender, pre-injury weekly hours worked, nursing occupation type; as well as the injury characteristics of the primary body injury location. Outcomes included days of incapacity and payment amount from the compensation scheme. As it was not requested in the data extraction application, the data set did not include information on the nature, mechanism of injury or agency of injury (Figure 1).

Victorian Health Services: Health service data collection extended from July 2017 until December 2021 (4.5 years) and was extracted from the VHIMS health service system²⁴. Staff injury inclusion criteria included a musculoskeletal injury by an adult (18+) member of the health or aged care workforce that occurred during staff-assisted patient/resident movement; exclusion criteria included non-musculoskeletal injuries or injuries that did not occur during staff-assisted patient/resident movement. Patient/resident falls, defined as "an event which results in a person coming to rest inadvertently on the ground or floor or other lower level"²⁵ inclusion criteria included a reported fall by an adult (18+) patient/resident that occurred during staff-assisted patient/resident movement; exclusion criteria included falls that did not occur during staff-assisted patient/resident movement.

Characteristics and outcomes: Incident data was extracted from all available data fields for the VHIMS staff or patient/resident incident report, including the free text responses that described the incident (one free text data field requested an incident summary, and the other free text data field requested incident details). Outcomes include the 7-items from the final version of the risk-identification coding framework that had been coded from the free-text responses (see below).

Analysis

WorkSafe Victoria: Claimant characteristics and injury characteristics have been presented descriptively as a number and percentage, or as a mean and standard deviation and as a median and range, as a complete cohort, and separately for part time (< 35 hours /week) and full time (≥ 35 hours /week) cohorts. The combined total of days on the scheme for all claimants was converted into lost hours by converting the number of days on the scheme, to the number of weeks on the scheme, and then multiplying this by the average pre-injury work hours per week. The payment amount was indexed by CPI so that all costs were presented as 2022 \$AUD (Australian dollars)²⁶. In addition, to determine a ratio for lost work compared to hours worked, for musculoskeletal

compensation claimants and the Victorian nursing and midwifery workforce, respectively, data from this study were compared to the Victorian nursing and midwifery workforce data ¹⁷.

Victorian Health Services: Coded health service data from the free text responses within the staff injury and patient/resident falls incidents were presented as a number and percentage, per the 7-item risk-identification framework. The number of incidents with low quality data in the free text responses were also reported as a number and a percentage (noting that low quality indicated minimal detail was provided in the free text responses of the incident report which limited understanding and interpretation of the incident).

Development of the risk-identification coding framework for the health service data

Development of the risk-identification coding framework occurred over several iterations and involved a registered nurse (RAG, more than 15 years clinical experience) and two physiotherapists (CG and NB, each with more than 15 years of clinical experience). The first iteration of the coding framework was based on the previously published ergonomic classification of TILE: task, individual, load and environment ^{14, 27}. Each iteration involved mapping the coding framework to a small number of cases, so the coding framework could be revised and refined. Once the risk-identification coding framework was finalised, CG and NB both coded a small number of incidents to assess the consistency of applying the framework to the incidents. Following confirmation of the consistency of applying the framework, all data were coded by CG and RAG, and were randomly checked by NB, with any disagreements being addressed via discussion. Details of the three stages to finalise the framework are detailed below and in Figure 2.

Stage 1: A small number of test injury and falls incidents were coded based on “TILE” (4-items: task, individual, load, and environment), noting that TILE is a common acronym used in manual handling programs to categorise key risk considerations ^{14, 27}. During this initial coding process, and via discussion between the research team, it was identified that *individual* could refer to risks associated with either the member of staff, or the patient/resident. As such, *individual* was expanded into *individual staff*, and *individual patient/resident*. Similarly, for environment, it was identified that this could refer to the fixed environment, or to equipment within the environment. This resulted in *environment* being expanded into *environment (fixed)*, and *equipment*.

Stage 2: A small number of test injury and falls incidents were coded based on “TIILEE” (6-items: task, individual staff, individual patient/resident, load, environment, and equipment). During this second coding process, and via discussion between the research team, it was identified that a small number of injury and falls incidents reported that staff conducted a risk assessment, either before, during or after the incident. Given the evidence that risk assessment is missing in most Australian health and aged care staff manual handling programs ²⁸, and that manual handling programs that include risk assessment may reduce staff injuries, compared to programs without risk assessment that are unlikely to reduce staff injuries ^{29, 30}, risk assessment was added to the coding framework.

Stage 3: With no other risk categories identified by the research team, the final coding framework included 7-items that could contribute to a staff musculoskeletal injury, or to a patient/resident fall, that occurred during staff assisted patient/resident movement. These were based on “RA-TIILEE” 7-items 1) risk assessment before, during or after the task, 2) the task itself, 3) the individual members of staff, 4) the individual patient or resident, 5) the load, 6) the environment, and 7) the equipment. For both the staff injuries, and the patient/resident falls, examples of incident reports were tabled as examples of each of the 7-items to guide the ongoing coding process (Appendix 2 and 3). Figure 1 details the stages of expanding and defining the categories that were included in the final 7-item coding framework.

Figure 2: Development of the categories for the coding framework

Results

Participants – Nurses and midwives with a musculoskeletal compensation claim

There were 1,936 musculoskeletal compensation claims for registered nurses and midwives across Victoria in the study period. The average number of accepted claims per year was 427.2 (SD 36.2); with a range of 380 to 471 per year. The mean age of claimants at the time of injury was 43.4 years (SD 12.7), 90% (n=1,741/1,936) were female, and pre-injury weekly hours worked was 31.8 (SD 7.6). The average days of incapacity while accessing the compensation scheme was 151.8 (SD 198.6) per claimant (or 21.7 weeks (SD 28.3)), with a combined total of 293,885 days for the 1,936 claimants over 4.5 years. The mean payment amount from the compensation scheme was \$AUD 33,297 (\$70,295), with a combined total of \$AUD 64,462,992 for the 1,936 claimants over 4.5 years (or \$14,325,109 per year).

Based on the combined total of 293,885 days on the scheme, or 41,984 weeks, there was a total of 1,335,077 lost hours. This equates to 676 FTE of missed work over 4.5 years due to nursing musculoskeletal compensation claims (or 150 FTE per year). Claimant and injury characteristics are reported in Table 1 as a complete cohort, and separately as part time (< 35 hours /week) and full time (≥ 35 hours /week) cohorts. In addition, for every 206 hours worked by the Victorian nursing workforce, there is 1 hour lost due to a musculoskeletal compensation claim (Table 2).

Table 1: Claimant details following an accepted musculoskeletal compensation claim

	All claimants, n=1,936	Part time claimants (< 35 hours /week), n=1,103	Full time claimants (≥ 35 hours /week), n=833
Age, mean (SD)	43 years (13)	43 years (13)	44 years (12)
Female, number (%)	1,741 (90%)	1,008 (91%)	733 (88%)
Pre-injury work hours, mean (SD) median (range)	31.8 (7.6) 32 (3 to 80)	26.8 (5.7) 28 (3 to 34)	38.5 (3.4) 38 (35 to 80)
Pre-injury weekly gross income, \$AUD mean (SD)* median (range)	\$1,134 (\$665) \$1,252 (\$0 to \$3,761)	\$1,045 (\$554) \$1,165 (\$22 to \$3,727)	\$1,252 (\$773) \$1,463 (\$22 to \$3,761)
Incapacity days, mean (SD) median (range)	151.8 (198.6) 75 (0 to 1,273)	160.2 (200.4) 89 (0 to 1,242)	140.7 (195.7) 62 (0 to 1,273)
Incapacity weeks,			

mean (SD)	21.7 (28.3)	22.9 (28.6)	20.1 (28.0)
median (range)	11 (0 to 182)	13 (0 to 177)	9 (0 to 182)
Compensation paid (weekly payments combined with compensation expenses), \$AUD			
mean (SD)*	\$33,297 (\$70,295)	\$32,965 (\$71,015)	\$33,376 (\$69,370)
median (range)	\$6,758 (\$0 to \$887,901)	\$7,044 (\$0 to \$887,901)	\$6,130 (\$0 to \$612,017)
Nursing occupation type, number (%)			
i. Nurse manager	57 (3%)	24 (2%)	33 (4%)
ii. Nurse educator and researcher	10 (1%)	< 10	< 10
iii. Registered nurse	1,712 (88%)	979 (89%)	733 (88%)
iv. Registered midwife	74 (4%)	61 (6%)	13 (2%)
v. Registered mental health nurse	70 (4%)	26 (2%)	44 (5%)
vi. Registered developmental disability nurse	13 (1%)	< 10	< 10
Location of first (primary) body injury, number (%)			
i. Neck	174 (9%)	98 (9%)	76 (9%)
ii. Trunk	981 (51%)	583 (53%)	398 (48%)
iii. Upper limb	590 (30%)	314 (28%)	276 (33%)
iv. Lower limb	180 (9%)	103 (9%)	77 (9%)
v. Multiple	11 (1%)	< 10	< 10

* \$AUD prior to 2022 has been inflated by the consumer price index to report 2022 financial data <https://www.rba.gov.au/calculator/annualDecimal.html>

Table 2: Lost work compared to hours worked, for musculoskeletal compensation claimants and the Victorian nursing workforce, respectively

	CLAIMANTS			WORKFORCE			RATIO
	Number	Average pre-injury hours, per week	Total lost hours, per week	Number ¹	Average hours worked, per week ²	Total hours worked, per week	Hours lost (claimants) to hours worked (workforce)
2017 ³	400	32.0 (SD 7.2)	12,800	74,307	33.4	2,481,854	1:194
2018	418	31.7 (SD 8.0)	13,261	78,029	33.4	2,606,169	1:197
2019	380	31.7 (SD 7.9)	12,044	81,901	33.5	2,743,684	1:228

2020	471	32.0 (SD 7.5)	15,086	89,085	33.2	2,957,622	1:196
2021	467	31.7 (7.1)	14,796	93,622	33.9	3,173,786	1:215
Average per year	427	31.8	13,597	83,389	33.5	2,792,623	1:206

¹ <https://www.nursingmidwiferyboard.gov.au/About/Statistics.aspx>;

² <https://hwd.health.gov.au/>

³ Extrapolated from 200 over 6 months to 400 over 12 months to allow the ratio calculation

Applying the coding framework to incidents where health service staff sustained a musculoskeletal injury

Prior to filtering the all-cause staff musculoskeletal injury data, to remove injuries that did not occur during patient/resident staff-assisted movement, an in-depth review of 144 consecutive all-cause staff musculoskeletal injuries was conducted. This review found that just over one-third (n=59/144; 41%) of this sub-set of all-cause injuries occurred during patient/resident staff-assisted movement.

Across the two health services, 748 staff injuries occurred during patient/resident staff-assisted movement. 197 incidents had low quality data (26%). There were 327 one-staff assist incidents (n=327/748; 44%), 241 two-staff assist incidents (n=241/748; 32%), with the remaining incidents involving three or more members of staff. Location of first (primary) body injury, and the type of patient/resident mobility being assisted, are detailed in Table 4. The most common body injury location was the trunk (449/748; 60%) followed by the upper limb (214/748; 27%). The most frequent type of activity being assisted was a transfer (e.g., from the bed to a chair; 342/748; 46%) followed by bed mobility (233/748; 31%).

Table 4: Location of first (primary) body injury and type of mobility being assisted

Injury descriptors	Number (n=748)	Percentage
Body location for the injury		
Neck	41	5%
Trunk	449	60%
Upper limb	214	27%
Lower limb	28	4%
Not specified	16	2%
Type of patient/resident mobility being assisted		
Bed mobility	233	31%

Transfers (e.g., from the bed to a chair)	342	46%
Walking	31	4%
Supporting standing (e.g., in the shower)	31	4%
Assisting mobility to prevent or support a fall ¹	44	6%
Transporting a patient ² (e.g., from ward to pathology)	37	5%
Moving a limb as a part of assisting mobility	11	1%
Not specified	19	3%

¹Assisting mobility to prevent or support a fall includes steadying a patient/resident while they are standing or moving with the intent of preventing or supporting a likely or actual fall. ²Transporting a patient includes all aspects of moving a patient from one area in the hospital to another. Manual handling tasks can include moving the wheelchair/trolley, adjusting the patient in the wheelchair/trolley, and assisting the patient on/off the wheelchair/trolley.

The most frequent factors contributing to staff musculoskeletal injuries during staff-assisted patient/resident movement included risk related to patient participation or behaviour (n=540/748, 72%), risk with the patient load (n=484/748, 65%), and risk with the planned task (n=339/748, 45%); with few injury reports documenting that a staff completed a risk assessment before, during or after the activity (n=26/748; 3%) (Table 5; Figure 3).

Table 5: Risk factors identified for each staff incident that occurred during staff-assisted patient/resident movement (2017-2022)

Risk factors identified	Number (a single incident can appear in more than one category)	Percentage
Did staff report a <u>risk assessment</u> was completed?	26	3%
Was there a RISK with the <u>Task?</u> (Yes)	339	45%
Was there a RISK with the <u>Individual – Staff?</u> (Yes)	67	9%
Was there a RISK with the <u>Individual – Patient</u> characteristics/ability to participate? (Yes)	540	72%
Was there a RISK with the <u>Load?</u> (Yes)	484	65%
Was there a RISK with the <u>Environment?</u> (Yes)	183	24%
Was there a RISK with the <u>Equipment?</u> (Yes)	113	15%

Applying the coding framework to incidents where health service patients/residents sustained a fall

All all-cause patient/resident falls data over the 4.5 years were initially reviewed to identify if the fall occurred during patient/resident staff-assisted movement, or not. This review found that just over one-quarter (n=1,935/7,179; 27%) of the all-cause falls occurred during patient/resident staff-assisted movement.

Across the two health services, there were 1,935 patient/resident falls that occurred during patient/resident staff-assisted movement. 182 incidents had low quality data (9%). There were 1,622 one-staff assist incidents (n=1,622/1,935; 84%), 241 two-staff assist incidents (n=241/1,935; 12%), with the remaining incidents involving three or more members of staff. The most frequent type of activity being assisted was transfers (748/1,935; 39%), followed by walking (584/1,935; 30%), general functional tasks where the patient/resident slid from a surface onto the floor e.g., when staff were assisting movement related to function, such as repositioning in a chair, getting dressed or showering, and the patient/resident fell (339/1,935; 18%), as well as assisted movement with the allied health team during therapy (221/1,935; 11%).

The most frequent factors which contributed to patient/resident falls during staff-assisted patient/resident movement include risks related to patient participation or behaviour (n=1,820/1,935; 94%), and risk with the patient load (n=1,062/1,935, 55%); with few reporting that staff completed a risk assessment of the activity (n=70/1,935; 4%) (Table 6; Figure 3). In addition, of the 1,935 patient/resident falls that occurred during staff-assisted movement, more than half (n=1,108/1,935; 57%) involved members of staff physically assisting the patient to the floor (or a lower surface) during the fall to prevent or reduce patient/resident injury.

Table 6: Risk factors identified for each patient/resident fall that occurred during staff-assisted patient/resident movement (2017-2022)

Risk factors identified	Number (a single incident can appear in more than one category)	Percentage
Did staff report a risk assessment was completed?	70	4%
Was there an apparent RISK with the Original Planned <u>Task</u> ? (Yes)	326	17%
Was there a RISK with the Individual – <u>Staff</u> ? (Yes)	184	10%
Was there a RISK with the Individual – <u>Patient</u> characteristics/ability to participate? (Yes)	1,820	94%
Was there a RISK with the <u>Load</u> ? (Yes)	1,062	55%
Was there a RISK with the <u>Environment</u> ? (Yes)	218	11%
Was there a RISK with the <u>Equipment</u> ? (Yes)	89	5%

To allow comparison between the risk factors for a staff injury and a patient/resident fall during assisted patient/resident movement, Figure 3 compares the frequency of risk category identified, and the frequency of incidents with a reported risk assessment, for each.

Figure 3: Comparing staff injury incidents, and patient/resident fall incidents, for the frequency of risk category identified

Discussion

The risk-identification coding framework developed and tested in this study identified key modifiable risks and can support future coding of health and aged care services incident data that relates to staff-assisted patient/resident movement to enhance understanding of the factors that contribute to nursing and midwifery staff musculoskeletal injuries and patient/resident falls. In addition, the application of the risk-identification coding framework to over 2,500 staff injury and patient/resident fall incidents in this study, can inform the development of new staff manual handling programs designed to reduce incidents associated with patient/resident assisted movement. Critically the study identified that risk assessment was rarely performed and that fall factors could have been modified with better more agile risk assessment.

We found that during patient/resident assisted movement, the factors that most frequently contributed to both nursing staff injuries and patient/resident falls were the individual patient/resident characteristics, as well as the patient/resident load. Despite most of the incident reports indicating the patient characteristics or behaviour contributed to the incidents, a very small portion of incident reports (<5%) noted that a risk assessment was completed either before, during or after the staff-assisted patient/resident movement, to mitigate the patient-related risk factors. In the context of all-cause injuries and falls, one-in-four all-cause patient/resident falls, and one-in-three all-cause staff musculoskeletal injuries occurred during staff-assisted patient/resident

movement, with the one-in-three all-cause staff musculoskeletal injuries data consistent with previously published literature ¹⁵.

There were three noteworthy findings from the incident coding process. First, while lifting equipment only contributed to 5% of patient/resident falls, it contributed to 15% of staff musculoskeletal injury incidents. Given the evidence that lifting equipment can contribute to lowering the incidence of staff musculoskeletal injuries (albeit a low certainty of evidence) ¹⁶, the lifting equipment was not expected to be identified as a contributing factor (e.g., contributing to wrist pain). Second, staff rarely documented the completion of a risk assessment in the incident reports (<5%). This finding was not unexpected as 92% of health and aged care services in Australia responding to a survey report that risk assessment is missing in part, or in whole, from their staff manual handling training program. Given there is evidence to support the inclusion of risk assessment in staff manual handling programs to reduce staff injuries ^{29, 30}, an implication of this finding is that future manual handling programs should include a focus on risk assessment skills, as well as emphasise the need to document in an incident report what risk assessment was completed before, during and after the patient/resident assisted movement. Third, while in the current study, staff most often assisted the patient/resident to the ground (or to a lower surface) during a fall (as compared to not assisting the patient/resident to the ground), current “Best Practice Guidelines for Australian Hospitals” do not state if staff should or should not assist the patient/resident to the ground during a fall³¹. The implication of this finding is that further research is urgently required to determine if staff should assist patients/residents to the floor when they are likely to fall, or actually falling, and if it is possible to do this safely for both patient/residents and staff.

The impact of nursing and midwifery workplace injuries on workforce shortages is significant, with the current study reporting 150FTE is lost to the Victorian workforce each year due to musculoskeletal compensation claims. Given that up to 90% of workplace injuries do not result in a compensation claim, and are either not reported or managed within the workplace, this 150FTE of lost work via compensation claims is just the tip of the iceberg ¹⁰⁻¹². A recent systematic review identified 12 studies, published between 2009 and 2019, that reported the effectiveness of applied policy options to manage shortages of nurses and midwives ¹³. Across the 12 studies, policies focussed on improving payment agreements, recruitment during emergencies, nursing residency programs, contracting systems, allowances for rural employment, as well as graduate and full-time recruitment incentives. However, none of the policies acknowledged the impact of workplace injuries on workforce shortages, nor included policy recommendations to address nursing and midwifery workplace injuries.

The risk-identification framework developed and tested in the current study has already contributed to a promising potential solution, known as the Risk Assessment for moving Individuals Safely (RAISE) manual handling program ¹⁴. Risk assessment is central to this recently developed innovative manual handling program that was designed to reduce workplace musculoskeletal injuries during staff-assisted patient/resident movement. Pilot RAISE studies conducted in the acute, rehabilitation and aged care settings have shown that staff who participate in the RAISE program demonstrate positive behaviour change at the bedside, specifically the inclusion of risk assessment during staff-assisted patient/resident movement, at both one and six months following the training ^{32, 33}.

While this study has multiple strengths, it also has several limitations. Strengths include the collection of both public and private health service data; and an extended timeframe of 4.5 years for the compensation claim and health service data across Victoria. Limitations include health service injury and falls data from only two Victorian health services; as well as an acknowledgment that the quality of the health service incident reports varied greatly (noting that low quality indicated minimal detail was provided in the free text responses of the incident report which limited understanding and interpretation of the incident). An additional recommendation going forward could be that institutions aim to produce improved reporting mechanisms of their incidents in the free text data fields, including a brief, but accurate, description of the arising incident with a

minimum information data set required, so that the true nature of the incident is documented. This may also facilitate the staff to more clearly document the presence of risk elements that potentially contributed to the incidents. This would also assist the work health and safety teams and managers (and researchers) who review the incidents to see incident trends more clearly, which would in turn highlight where risk management strategies are deficient and need modification (or should be directed). In addition, it is possible that reporting of incidents potentially lacks some integrity in the first instance, as staff may not necessarily wish to declare all that has occurred, especially if risks are apparent, but have been ignored.

Conclusion

Nursing and midwifery workforce musculoskeletal injuries come at a great cost to the individual and the nursing workforce. Developing a coding framework to identify risk factors that contributed to staff injuries and patient/resident falls, sustained during staff-assisted patient/resident movement, can support clinicians and researchers in developing data-driven solutions to this high-risk activity.

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